

Lasers for gas sensing

Fig. 1. Gas detection limits for absorbance 10^{-5} after [2]

The research project 3.4 “Testing and validation of lasers for gas sensing” for Experienced Researcher (ER) located in Procal as part of WP3 in MC ITN Prophet project was in direct relationship with Continuous Emission Monitoring (CEM) gas analyzers manufactured by Procal, and company future research and commercial strategy.

Procal would like to supplement mature Non-Dispersive InfraRed (NDIR) technique with laser based gas detection technique, that would allow sensitive detection of selected gas species.

The ER role in project was to contribute to understanding, design and development of new gas sensor instrumentation, including mathematical models, optics, electronics and control software appropriate for laser-based gas detection.

This report is divided into three main parts. The first part is focused on introduction of basic ideas essential for gas sensing such as:

- gas absorption lines and spectroscopic databases
- techniques of gas detection with lasers: Tunable Diode Laser Absorption Spectroscopy (TDLAS)
- description of TDLAS with Wavelength Modulation Spectroscopy
- types of noise in TDLAS

The first part is concluded with description of general requirements that should be fulfilled by lasers for gas sensing.

The second part is devoted to analysis of commercially available lasers for gas detection, and measurements that were conducted to assess their performance.

The third part is devoted to work on optoelectronic modules for gas sensing.

1. Lasers for gas sensing

1. Spectroscopy Databases and Gas Lines

Understanding and characterising the amount and wavelength-dependence of absorption by molecules in vapour mixtures is essential for laser based gas sensing.

Calculations of absorption by gas mixtures rely on molecular spectral lines databases such as HITRAN (**H**igh **R**esolution **T**ransmission), GEISA to provide information about the spectral properties of molecules present in the atmosphere. Such calculations allow to select optimal wavelength of lasers for detection of gas species in particular gas mixture.

There are a few software/algorithms for generation line-by-line spectrum from Hitran database:

HAWK, LinePak, GenLn2, LBLRTM, UMBCL, Py4CATs.

Generally this algorithms are starting from Hitran data, and lineshape functions (Gauss, Lorentzian or Voigt, pressure and temperature dependent) and calculate sum of lineshapes, for every line in selected wavelength range.

To facilitate understanding of the gas lines physics, I wrote my own scripts (R language) which operate on source HITRAN database, and generates absorbance or transmittance profiles as a function of wavelength.

Fig. 2. Comparison of O_2 absorption calculated with R script, and Py4CATS. Small discrepancies are caused by more lines (wider wavelength range) included in Py4CATS calculation.

Developed scripts was used for selecting optimal gas lines for HCl (fig. 3, 4) and NH_3 detection in environment corresponding to combustion exhaust, where Procal analyzers are used.

Fig. 3. Wide spectrum of HCl, CO₂ and H₂O absorption around 1.74 μ m.

Fig. 4. Narrow spectrum of absorption, shows optimal HCl detection line at $\sim 1.742\mu$ m.

Comparison of generated gas spectrum with Fabry-Perot laser (fig. 5) showed, that signal change due to absorption by thin HCl gas lines will be buried under large signal from unabsorbed FP laser radiation.

Fig. 5. Calculated absorption of FP laser signal by HCl gas lines.

Software for calculation of gas absorption may also be used to study physical phenomena in conventional NDIR gas detection technique, such as influence of optical filter position on absorbance from interfering gases or influence of temperature changes on measured absorbance.

2. Selection of gas detection technique

Optical methods for gas sensing are usually based on spectroscopy. The examples of spectroscopic gas detection techniques are Non-Dispersive Infrared (NDIR), Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR), Differential Optical Absorption Spectroscopy (DOAS), and finally Tunable Diode Laser Absorption Spectroscopy (TDLAS).

The main focus of work in Procal was given to TDLAS, as it is a technique of choice in industry applications. In TDLAS[1] narrow linewidth laser diode is scanned through a selected gas absorption line with very high resolution (fig. 11).

Fig. 6. Example of scanning across oxygen gas absorption line (top), non-linear Levenberg-Marquardt fitting to slope+Lorentzian lineshape (middle), and residuals from fitting (bottom).

Such a high resolution is advantageous in a number of ways: a large signal to noise ratio, specificity to the target gas, and finally real time operation stemming from high modulation frequency of laser diodes.

The most industrially proven TDLAS implementations are:

- Direct Absorption Spectroscopy (DAS),
- Wavelength Modulation Spectroscopy (WMS),
- Off-Axis Integrated Cavity Output Spectroscopy (OA-ICOS)
- Photoacoustic Spectroscopy (PAS)

Difference between DAS and WMS is schematically shown on fig. 7 and 8.

Fig. 7. The schematic plot of direct spectroscopy and wavelength modulation spectroscopy, reproduced from [2].

Fig. 8. Schematical comparison between direct spectroscopy and wavelength modulation spectroscopy. The non-constant laser intensity during tuning has almost no influence on the harmonic spectrum, reproduced from [2].

In DAS (fig. 7a) laser current ramp increases light intensity and temperature, which cause change of the refractive index of layers inside laser. Refractive index change leads to tuning of laser wavelength across absorption line. Gas absorbance is responsible for small volleys on the large background resulted from the change of laser power as function of its current.

3. TDLAS-WMS

To succinctly give general description of WMS I will quote here excellent PhD of Jia Chen[2]: "WMS due to its advantages of efficient noise suppression, i.e. insusceptible to 1/f noise, and removal of the laser amplitude modulation [3] in the measured data. As shown in Fig. 7-9, in addition to a slow current (or wavelength) sweep, a small and significantly faster sinusoidal modulation with frequency f_m is applied (typically in the kHz range). The gas absorption converts

the frequency modulation to an intensity modulation. Because the gas absorption spectrum is a strongly nonlinear function of wavelength, the resulting amplitude modulation is not sinusoidal any more, but contains harmonic components at multiple of the modulation frequency f_m . Using a lock-in amplifier, the detector signal is decomposed into its harmonic components. The formation of first-/second-harmonic spectrum is schematically shown in Fig. 9.”

Fig. 9. The steps of creation of first-/second-harmonic gas spectrum, reproduced from [2].

To obtain better insight into WMS signal generation, I would refer readers to [webpage](#) [4] of prof. Tom O'Haver, with spreadsheet that allows to simulate WMS signals.

“The second harmonic spectrum, i.e. second harmonic component of the gas absorption is usually used for signal evaluation. Although in theory any harmonic spectrum may be chosen, the influence of the laser AM on the second harmonic spectrum is small enough compared to the first harmonic while the amplitude of the second harmonic is still relatively large compared to the higher harmonics. The experimental setup of wavelength modulation spectroscopy is shown in Fig. 10.

Fig. 10: The experimental setup of wavelength modulation spectroscopy, reproduced from [2].

“In the laboratory, the ramp signal and high frequency sinusoidal modulation are generated by the function generator and the sum of the two are injected to the laser controller, which controls the laser current. The detected intensity of the photodiode is converted into a current and amplified by a trans-impedance amplifier. Lock-In amplifier is a mixer and is used to decompose the detector signal into its harmonic components. To obtain the second-harmonic spectrum, the intensity at $2f$ is divided by the intensity at DC, so the effect of the varying laser intensity is removed. This is a significant advantage over direct spectroscopy.”

In practice it seems, that properly implemented WMS and DAS could give very similar performance in systems, where laser RIN is the main, dominating noise effect. WMS places less stringent requirements on ADC resolutions. This was elegantly proved by Lins et al., first by simulations[5], and later confirmed by building system with software switching between WMS and DAS[5], [6].

Exhaustive description of WMS signal decomposition was given in [3] by Axner, Kluczynski, Lindberg and Gustaffson.

Fig. 11. TDLAS-WMS principle. Top: HCl and H₂O gas absorption lines, around 1743nm. Middle: Signal on photodetector during a sweep of VCSEL laser diode current from 0 to 8mA. Bottom: First and second derivative of detector signal. On resonance signal is proportional to gas absorption.

One of the major constraints imposed by Procal is integration of laser based gas detection technique with currently used NDIR technique, which means that existing, 1m optical pathlength, double-pass gas cell need to be used. This requirement excludes OA-ICOS and PAS techniques, leaving TDLS DAS and WMS techniques.

Fig. 12: Calculated SNR for TDLS and OA-ICOS with two different preamplifiers. $P_0=20mW$, single pass absorption $1e-5$, $L=0.3m$, $T_m=1$, $C_p=1$, $R=0.99$. [7]

Analysis of signal-to-noise ratio in TDLS and OA-ICOS made by reproducing calculations from Dyroff [7] show that for short, fixed pathlength S/N ratio in TDLS detection is larger than in ICOS (fig. 12) which justify selection of TDLS as gas sensing technique for Procal.

4. TDLAS-WMS model

Before Prophet project Procal was using the simplest variant of signal processing in calibration domain (absorbance vs concentration) based on detection of the peak absorbance or the area under the absorbance peak, and use a measured reference curve to get absorbance using linear curve fit.

This method is easy to implement and is used in simple sensors, but its accuracy suffer from inherent drifts in the sensor due to optical component and laser temperature changes.

Absorbance curve fit with an analytical model function appears to be much more flexible approach, and it facilitate deeper understanding of the gas absorption phenomena in comparison to method based on a measured reference curve distorted by noise.

Participation in MIRSENS 2 conference allowed to meet prof. Ove Axner and dr Pawel Kluczynski, developers of the analytical model for recorded WMS harmonic signals, which includes the effect of laser residual amplitude modulation (RAM) in the measured spectra.

The invitation to training in Umea from prof. Axner allowed to meet his PhD student Jonas Westberg who helped to gain better understanding of analytical approach to WMS developed at Umea University, and reproduce model for TDLS-WMS absorption fitting in spectral domain (intensity/absorbance vs wavelength), described in [3][8].

Especially interesting was RAM effects (fig. 13), which are strong in DFB lasers, but VCSEL lasers for HCl and O₂ detection used in Procal have RAM effects as well.

Fig. 13. Influence of laser intensity modulation (1st order = 2, 2nd order = 0.5) on 2-f signal shape.

Fig. 13 shows how 1st and 2nd order intensity modulation coefficients affect 2-f signal. 1st order intensity modulation cause asymmetric “skew” of the 2-f profile, but it didn't change peak absorption, whereas 2nd order intensity modulation decreases maximum and minimum of the 2-f signal.

Fig. 14: Fitting to signal+noise with non-linear least squares Levenberg-Marquard method to TDLS-WMS model.

Fig. 14 shows fitting of the 2-f signal + noise with model. The same model could be used for multicomponent fitting.

Good example of fitting in TDLAS could be found in work of Hangauer et al. [9][10].

5. Noise types in TDLAS

Requirements to lasers for gas sensing ensue from noise types that limit TDLAS detectability, thus a brief description of TDLAS noises will be given.

On the most general level Relative Intensity Noise (RIN) is defined as additional intensity fluctuations of laser diode output power (excess noise, not related to noise from photodetector), that occur even if constant injection current is applied [6]. RIN could be calculated as ratio of LD variance of power to squared mean optical LD power, and divided by noise bandwidth. It's units are [1/Hz], and range span from 1e-11 up to 1e-16 1/Hz.

Fig. 15 shows simple experiment, which helps understand RIN noise, and how it differ from noise in photodetectors.

Fig. 15. Photodiode PD is illuminated by laser diode LD with constant injection current. Signal from PD is detected by transimpedance preamplifier TIA, and then visualized on scope as variance of voltage u_{rms} and mean voltage \bar{U} . Distance between LD and PD is decreased, to study changes in variance and mean value of signal, as power (photo-current) detected by photodiode increases [7].

Uncollimated laser diode radiation (constant current and LD temperature) is detected by photodiode PD with preamplifier TIA, and visualized on scope. Distance between LD and PD is

changed, in such a way, to stay in linear range of TIA. Experiment could be described with following equation:

$$RMS\ Noise_{Total} [A/\sqrt{(Hz)}] = \sqrt{RIN \cdot D_0^2 + 2 \cdot q \cdot (D_0 + I_{dark}) + 4 \cdot k_B \cdot T_{PA} / R_v} \quad (1.1)$$

where D_0 is detector DC photocurrent, q - electron charge, I_{dark} - dark current of photodiode, k_B - Boltzmann constant, T_{PA} - temperature of preamplifier, R_v - transimpedance gain of preamplifier.

Fig. 16. Noise current density as a function of photocurrent D_0 for $RIN=1e-14$ 1/Hz, $R_v=1.5e4$ V/A, $T_{PA}=296K$, $I_{dark}=2nA$.

Fig. 17. Noise spectral density as a function of photocurrent D_0 for the same parameters as in fig. 16.

Fig. 16 shows, that as we decrease distance between LD and PD, both photocurrent and total noise increases. Below $3\mu A$ total noise is dominated by contribution from preamplifier noise, between $3\mu A$ and $30\mu A$ total noise is limited by shot noise contribution, and above $30\mu A$ RIN noise is the main factor responsible for total noise.

Additionally, equation 1.1 shows, that total noise have form of quadratic function with D_0 as variable, where RIN act as quadratic coefficient, shot noise adds linear dependence on D_0 , and noises from photodiode dark current and transimpedance forms free term.

Transformation of equation 1.1 by dropping square root, and dividing by D_0^2 gives equation for noise power density [2] (NPD) plotted in fig. 17. We could treat NPD as noise to signal ratio ($1/SNR$), where SNR is equal to squared DC photocurrent divided by variance of current noise. If we assume that absorbed power is linearly dependent on laser diode power and DC photocurrent, then it means, that RIN noise sets a limit for maximum SNR ratio in detection system, which couldn't be enlarged by increase of laser power.

Usually RIN noise have $1/f^\alpha$ spectral power density with $\alpha=0.5-1.6$, therefore increase of modulation frequency in TDLAS-WMS moves detection frequency into region with smaller RIN. Similarly, in DAS RIN contribution could be lowered by decreasing time of the single ramp, which shifts the first passband of comb-like transmission spectrum of the averaging process to ramp frequency, and at the same time allows to increase amount of averages per fixed unit of time [6].

As we now have some understanding, how RIN noise is measured, and why it is important, we could analyse in more detail physical origins of excess noises related to lasers.

In theory RIN noise consist of spontaneous emission radiation and laser-mode competition, but in practice a number of physical effects could contribute to RIN noise measurement.

If we would record (experiment on fig. 15) photocurrent as a function of time for fixed distance between LD and PD, we would be able to see that it consist of three types of noise in TDLAS[11]:

fundamental white noise (DL quantum noise), flicker noise and drift (slow baseline change). It is useful to show their effects on Allan Deviation or Allan Variance plot [12] (fig. 18).

Fig. 18. Allan plot of relative photocurrent noise as function of averaging time for baseline drift limited TDLS system[21]

Fig. 19. Suppression of flicker noise[13]

White noise is caused by laser diode quantum noise (intensity and frequency), and could be reduced by increase of averaging time. It sets fundamental limit of sensitivity. Influence of flicker and drift (slow baseline change) noises couldn't be limited by taking longer time averages, as their spectrum isn't uniform (white). The only way of reducing their effects is to identify their physical origin.

Fundamental origins of flicker noise are excitation current density fluctuations, and nonlinear behaviour of laser diodes [13]. Limitation of flicker noise is possible with measurement of laser radiation coming from 0° angle (fig. 19) or by collecting all laser radiation, but the latter is impossible to achieve in practice.

Drift noise is more complicated, and at least 7 physical origins could be found:

- B1: diode laser active area conductivity in-homogeneity,
 - interaction of electromagnetic field standing wave with inhomogeneity of excess carrier concentration.
 - not all diodes have such drift
 - baseline due to B1 is stable, therefore it could be subtracted from future measurements
 - baseline is stable, when electromagnetic field standing wave is stable which leads to requirements: **temperature stability of LD better than 1e-5 K, and laser diode current stability better than 0.1μA**
- B2: excitation current density fluctuations,
 - fundamental and common for all DL types
 - slowly changing with time
 - similar requirements for temperature and current stability as B1
 - changing with different directions/angles in DL diagram (like flicker noise)
- B3: light scattering inside DL active area,
- B4: light scattering inside DL module,

- B5: fiber leakage modes,
- B6: optical feedback,
- B7: interference due to reflection and scattering in optical scheme.

Suppressing B1 and B2 type of slow baseline change (drift) imposes very stringent requirements on laser temperature control system, and laser current driver.

Fig. 20. Origins of B3, B4, B5 and B6 types of drift. [21].
Laser diode with good quality single mode fiber pigtail and FC/APC to avoid drift origins [21].

Optical fibers available for lasers in near infrared range could alleviate problems related to B3, B4, B5, and B6 types of drift (fig. 20). Studying drift behaviour as a function of distance between laser output and detector, could indicate, what type of drift dominates in system (fig. 21).

Fig. 21. Drift of baseline as a function of distance between fiber output and photodetector for different drift origins [21].

6. Summary of requirements for TDLAS lasers

The key element of near infrared TDLAS analyzer is a laser diode. When starting to select a laser diode, the first task is to select single mode laser with a large side mode suppression ratio (SMSR~30dB). Such a laser diode by a combination of base temperature and drive current could be tuned to the selected absorption line of gas to be monitored.

The power of such LD in analytical channel should be limited to ~5mW, to not optically saturate gas molecules along measurement pathlength.

A matter of critical importance is packaging of laser diode chip, as proper package could limit B3, B4, B5 and B6 types of drift noise that would appear as RIN noise in gas analyser. Moreover, laser diode temperature stability, and subsequently B1, B2 types of laser diode drift noises depends on product of thermal resistance and capacitance of laser diode package and on delay of temperature propagation between laser diode and thermoelectric cooler (TEC).

Package of choice (fig. 22) for gas sensing laser diode would be butterfly housing with single mode fiber pigtail, built-in optical isolator that would suppress back-reflections 30-50dB, and photodiode with etalon in the path of beam. Etalon with photodiode allows locking laser to gas absorption line to add temperature and frequency stabilisation of laser diode, which in principle enable reaching fundamental limits of RIN.

Fig. 22. Schematic of the DFB laser module with wavelength monitoring function integrated into 14-pin butterfly package after [20].

Unfortunately, manufacturers of laser diodes for gas sensing applications rarely quote RIN levels for their products, as they probably do not have optical setups with laser temperature/frequency stabilisation, that would allow them to measure low levels of RIN noise.

Very low levels of RIN noise should be easier to achieve within Quantum Dot (QD) and Quantum Dash (QDash) lasers, that in principle have many advantages over Quantum Well (QW) lasers:

- wavelength determined by the energy levels of the dots, and not band gap energy [14]
- material and differential gain 2-3 times higher than Quantum Well (QW) laser diodes
- low power at high frequency operation
- low threshold current
- superior temperature stability of the threshold current
- reduced leakage from active region by suppression of diffusion from

Although in practice we see constant progress in parameters of QD/QDash lasers, realizing all benefits of this low dimensional structures requires significant technology advancements.

QD or Qdash lasers could have RIN noise as low as -160dB at 1.55 μ m, and values between -145 up to -150dB are measured routinely in Alcatel-Thales laboratory, which is one of the members of the Prophet consortium.

2. Gas detection

1. Vertilas VCSEL laser for HCl detection at 1.742 μ m

Before Prophet project Procal was investigating in internal project possibility of introducing TDLS sensors into their NDIR device for detecting selected gases, which are hard to detect with NDIR technique. Their introduction would allow to enter waste incinerators and large power combustion plants with gaseous turbines. HCl was one of the gases that need to be detected with range of about 0-9ppm.

To develop TDLS sensor for HCl detection 2 Vertilas VCSEL lasers with TEC were acquired. First was without window, and was damaged due to water freezing on top of laser chip shortly after purchase. Second laser was still operational at start of Prophet project, and available for TDLAS measurements.

Laser LIV and spectrum vs heatsink temperature are shown in fig. 23 and 24, respectively.

Fig. 23. VCSEL Light and Voltage vs Current characteristic.

Fig. 24. HCl VCSEL spectrum vs temperature.

Comparison of spectrum in fig. 3 and 15 show, that by proper selection of TEC temperature, laser could be tuned through HCl absorption line at 1742.3nm, with low interference from water lines.

The main tasks for this HCl gas detection were to familiarize with TDLS, establish limit of detection in current setup, and propose how it could be improved.

Schematic of the TDLS setup is shown in fig. 27, whereas equipment parameters are in tab. 1.

Optical setup was composed of (fig. 25 and 26), laser light was collimated by lens, reflected from mirror, and directed into measurement tube where beam passed through two lenses, and reflected from mirror. Reflected beam passed again two lenses, folded on small mirror, and focused by lens

on Hamamatsu G8371-01 detector (fig. 28 and 29). 6% HCl gas cell was placed in return beam, to obtain HCl absorption lines.

Fig. 25. Simulation of optical beam in TDLS setup.

Fig. 26. Laser on top, detector bottom, tube with gas on right.

Fig. 27: Schematic of TDLS gas analyzer for HCl detection

Tab. 1. Main parameters of the TDLS setup equipment.

	Fun. Gen. TG2000_1	Fun. Gen. TG2000_2		Laser driver (VITC 002)		LIA SciTec 420
Waveform	Triangle	Sine			Sensitivity	30mV
Frequency	120Hz	60 kHz			Time constant	100µs
Amplitude	112mV _{p-p}	17mV _{p-p}	Current	3mA+0.5mA	X and Y offsets	~0
DC offset	0mV	0mV			Output Main Phase	X or R
			SET Laser (P2 screw)	0.42 V (~4.2mA)	Phase Shift	0°
			Current limit (P1 screw)	~0.6V=6mA		100°
			Laser Temp = SET THERM(P4 screw)	26.7 C		

■ Electrical and optical characteristics (Typ. unless otherwise noted)

Type No.	Measurement Condition	Spectral response range λ	Peak sensitivity wavelength λ_p	Photo sensitivity S $\lambda=\lambda_p$	Dark current I _D V _R =1 V		Cut-off frequency f _c V _R =1 V R _L =50 Ω -3 dB (MHz)	Terminal capacitance C _t V _R =1 V f=1 MHz (pF)	Shunt resistance R _{sh} V _R =10 mV (MΩ)	D* $\lambda=\lambda_p$ (cm·Hz ^{1/2} /W)	NEP $\lambda=\lambda_p$ (W/Hz ^{1/2})
	Element temperature (°C)				Typ. (nA)	Max. (nA)					
G8421-03	25	0.9 to 1.9			30	300	100	8	1.5	5 × 10 ¹¹	9 × 10 ⁻¹⁴
G8421-05					50	500	80	20	1		1.5 × 10 ⁻¹³
G8371-01					100	1000	40	80	0.5		2 × 10 ⁻¹³
G8371-03					2000	20000	3	800	0.05		8 × 10 ⁻¹³

Fig. 28. Parameters of G8371-01 detector

Type No.	Measurement Condition	Spectral response range λ	Peak sensitivity wavelength λ_p	Photo sensitivity S $\lambda=\lambda_p$		Dark current I _D V _R =1 V		Cut-off frequency f _c V _R =1 V R _L =50 Ω -3 dB (MHz)	Terminal capacitance C _t V _R =1 V f=1 MHz (pF)	Shunt resistance R _{sh} V _R =10 mV (kΩ)	D* $\lambda=\lambda_p$ (cm·Hz ^{1/2} /W)	NEP $\lambda=\lambda_p$ (W/Hz ^{1/2})
	Element temperature (°C)			Min. (A/W)	Typ. (A/W)	Typ. (µA)	Max. (µA)					
G8423-03	25	1.2 to 2.6				2	20	60	40	30	5 × 10 ¹⁰	7 × 10 ⁻¹³
G8423-05						5	50	50	60	15		1 × 10 ⁻¹²
G8373-01						15	75	15	200	3		2 × 10 ⁻¹²
G8373-03						150	1500	1.5	1800	0.3		8 × 10 ⁻¹²

Fig. 29. Parameters of G8371-01 detector

Digital oscilloscope was used for visualization of the measurements, whereas NI CompactRIO and Labview 8.4 was used for data acquisition and processing. Learning programming in LabView was one of the trainings that Procal engineers provided to Prophet postdoc.

Rising slope of TG2000_1 (aux out, blue on fig. 30) square train was used to trigger on DAQ acquisition (100kHz = sampling every 0.01ms), and at the same time TG2000_1 (main out, red on fig. 30) triangle waveform reaches half of its slope. Therefore pre-triggered acquisition was used, where 200samples (2ms) are collected before trigger, and 300 samples (3ms) after trigger, to get 500 samples (5ms). In such mode, collection of whole rising slope of triangle, and quarter of decreasing slope, is conducted. It would be worth to switch to sawtooth waveform, to get more frequent measurements of 2f shape.

Fig. 30. Triangle waveform and square train from TG2000_1 waveform generator used to sweep laser through absorption line and trigger data acquisition.

Conducted series of measurements revealed that Vertilas laser wavelength is very sensitive to changes of laser heatsink temperature, which was manifested as drift of maximum of the 2f shape in sampling range window (fig. 31).

Fig. 31. Maximum of 2f shape is drifting in sampling range window.

Laser holder design inherited from Procal internal project was reviewed, and serious flaws in the design were found (fig. 32). The laser radiator/heatsink was thermally insulated from bracket, and rough surface of heatsink contact to TO-5 can laser diode do not provide good thermal dissipation.

Fig. 32. Original design of the VCSEL laser mount

Laser mount was designed from scratch (fig. 33), which gave opportunity to train postdoc in usage of CAD tools (DraftSight) for design of opto-mechanical components.

Following manufacturing, new mount was tested in the TDLS setup, to verify whether stability of laser wavelength is improved (fig. 34 and 35).

Tests showed that, this time not only $2f$ maximum position is drifting with ambient temperature, but the maximum value of $2f$ is decreasing (fig. 34).

24h stability test showed perfect correlation of $2f$ max location changes with ambient temperature, whereas thermistor temperature was stable (green on fig. 35, noise due to long wires, and too small capacitor in measurement circuit).

Fig. 33. Laser mount designed for HCl laser.

Fig. 34. 2f max and amplitude drift during 24h stability test.

Fig. 35. Recorded 2f max location (left y axis), and ambient and laser thermistor temperatures.

Estimation of laser temperature changes from 2f max shape drift.

From Thorlabs specification typical current tuning coefficient of laser is 0.7 nm/mA. We were applying 112mV amplitude, 125Hz triangle waveform to laser driver input to sweep laser wavelength through HCl absorption band. Laser driver specs describe that 100mV corresponds to 1mA of laser current.

$1.12\text{mA} \cdot 0.7\text{nm/mA} = 0.784\text{nm}$ This is roughly width of wavelength spectrum swept by laser.

125Hz of triangle waveform corresponds to 8ms period (fig. 30)

400 samples = laser sweep, therefore $0.784\text{nm}/400\text{samples} = 1.96\text{pm}$ per sample.

Fig. 35 shows that day/night temperature variation cause shift of 15-20 samples of 2f maximum, which corresponds to $1.96\text{pm} \cdot 20\text{samples} = 39.2\text{pm}$. Temperature tuning coefficient from Vertilas laser specs 0.11 nm/K.

Therefore it can be concluded, that observed drift corresponds to laser module temperature variations of $39.2/1000/0.11 = 0.356\text{ K}$.

To put above result in perspective, good laser stability requires temperature stabilization to mK range, and state of the art setups stabilize laser temperature to 10^{-5}K range [14].

When it was confirmed, that poor stability of the laser wavelength is not caused by improper radiator/mount, examination of the laser and TEC packaging in TO-5 can was conducted (fig. 36).

Fig. 36. Packaging of laser, thermistor and TEC in TO-5 can, found from Vertilas website, corresponding to HCl laser that we inspected under microscope.

Examination revealed, that the root cause of laser temperature instability is related to wire connected to top of the thermistor. This wire creates direct heat path between pin (red line) and top plate of thermistor. For example, when heatsink temperature increase, thermistor receive increased heat flux. Its temperature starts to increase, and to keep it constant PID system increases TEC current to cool more TEC's cold stage. In the result TEC stage are colder, and laser temperature also decreases.

To brake thermal link between thermistor and heatsink, the thermistor wire should be connected to isolated pad on TEC stage first, and then a second wire should connect the pad to thermistor (blue line). In this way thermistor will have temperature equal to TEC top stage, and laser temperature will be more stable.

To conclude, investigation of the limits of detection revealed, that the HCl laser packaging do not allow to stabilize temperature of the laser to degree required for sensitive gas detection.

A month later, during [International Nano-Optoelectronics Workshop 2013](#) I met prof. M.C. Amann, co-founder of Vertilas. After his lecture, during coffee break, I described him the problem with laser stability, and he admitted, that early Vertilas lasers might had problems with temperature stability on TEC, but since that time Vertilas improved their lasers substantially [15]. He contacted me with member of Vertilas, who offered discount for replacement laser. Interestingly, price for replacement was higher, than the price paid for the first laser.

2. O₂ laser tests

Second laser that was available at start of Prophet project in Procal, was 763 nm VCSEL laser (Avalon Photonics). It was bought to test possibility of detecting oxygen with TDLS technique (fig. 37). Laser parameters are summarized in fig. 38. Oxygen absorption lines in the range accessible with this laser are shown in fig. 2 and 40.

Fig. 37. Output power vs laser current, and side mode suppression characteristics of 763 nm laser, vs wavelength.

Parameter*	Symbol	Conditions	Ratings			Units
			Min	Typ	Max	
VCSEL						
Threshold current	I_{th}		1.0	3.0	4.0	mA
Operating current	I_{op}	$P = 300\mu W$	2.0	4.0	5.5	mA
Operating voltage	V_{op}	I_{op}		2.4	3.5	V
Differential resistance	R_{op}		100	130	250	Ω
Optical output power (max SM)	P_{sm}	SMSR = 20dB	0.4	0.6		mW
Slope efficiency	η	I_{op}	0.1	0.3	0.4	W/A
Side mode suppression	SMSR	I_{op}	20			dB
Emission wavelength	λ	$P = 400\mu m$	758.0		765.0	nm
Beam divergence	θ	FWHM		13		$^{\circ}$
Linewidth	$\Delta\nu$	I_{op}			30	MHz
Relative intensity noise	RIN	$I_{op}, f = 5kHz$			-110	dB/Hz
Temperatur tuning coefficient	$\delta\lambda/\delta T$	I_{op}		0.06		nm/K
Current tuning coefficient	$\delta\lambda/\delta I$	$I_{op} + 0.5mA$		0.3		nm/mA

SM = single mode; MM = multi mode; SMSR = side mode suppression ratio; FWHM = full-width half-maximum

Fig. 38. Parameters of 763 nm laser

First the stability of the laser wavelength was tested, to see whether a clear difference between HCl and O₂ laser is visible. Laser stability was tested over weekend in setup similar to the one from fig. 27, but no reference cell was needed, as oxygen absorption lines was visible from from air in gas cell, and air along laser path in instrument head.

The other difference was, that this time DAS signal was recorded as well, without LIA. Ambient temperature, laser temperature, and raw signal from preamplifier during laser sweep was recorded by LabView.

Fig. 39. Hitran plot of linestrength vs wavelength for oxygen at 1bar.

Fig. 40. Oxygen absorption lines around 763nm wavelength for concentration of 20.946% and 1m pathlength at 1bar.

Data from Hitran2012 for Oxygen absorption lines was generated, and inspected, to see what absorption could be expected (fig. 40).

Fig. 41. Laser current sweep through oxygen absorption lines around 763nm (0-400 samples).

Preliminary sweep of laser diode current, to see absorption lines (fig. 40). Red lines showing selected range for short laser sweep, to measure more accurately single isolated line (fig. 42).

Fig. 42. Narrow laser scan of single oxygen absorption line.

Algorithm [3] for fitting measured absorption line with Lorentzian model was tested on the measured data to separate absorption line information from residuals (fig. 43 and 44).

Fig. 43. Fit with Lorentzian lineshape model to averaged 400 scans of oxygen absorption line. Parameters of fit: ny_0 , S , gL , a , b , c : 0.491, 0.008, 0.025, -0.008, 0.933, 1.439 respectively. ax^2+bx+c – parameters of the baseline. ny_0 – location of the max on scan range scale, S – linestrength, gL – broadening coefficient.

Fig. 44. Residuals from fitting with Lorentzian lineshape model single scan, and averaged 400 scans.

Series of measurements conducted to estimate stability of the setup. Short term stability was assessed by measurement of signal over 0.1s range time, with laser on, but without triangular modulation waveform (fig. 45).

Fig. 45. Signal variation over 0.1s time.

Ratio (dI/I) of standard deviation (2.18mV) to mean (1.659V) signal could be used as rough indication of sensitivity of the TDLS setup.

				S' [cm-2/atm]	S' [cm-2/atm]
				1.00E-003	1
	dl/l	ptot, atm	chi(v), 1/cm-1	crel*L, ppm*m	crel*L, ppm*m
DAS	5E-3	1	5	1E+4	1E+1
	5E-3	0.1	50	1E+4	1E+1
WMS	5E-6	1	5	1E+1	1E-2
	5E-6	0.1	50	1E+1	1E-2

Fig. 46. Reproduced from [22] tab. 4.1. "Order-of-magnitude minimum detectable rel.*L-values (in unit of ppm·m) for two typical types of transition (with integrated (gas) line strength, S?, of 10-3 and 1 cm-2/atm, respectively) detected by DAS and WMS assumed to have minimum detectable absorbances of 5×10-3 and 5×10-6, respectively."

This ratio is around 1.3e-3 in this case, which might be expected for such unrefined DAS TDLS setup. Sometimes it is used to calculate estimated detectability of the setup, as shown in fig. 46.

To establish wavelength stability of the laser, 3-day long measurements were conducted (fig. 47 and 48). Oxygen absorption line peak location detected as crossing through 0 of 1-f signal (fig. 47).

Fig. 47. Examples of 1f shape recorded during 3 day test used to detect crossing through 0, between min and max, as a way to observe drift of laser wavelength.

Fig. 48. Location of 2f max (1f zero crossing) during the stability experiment.

No dependence of laser wavelength on ambient temperature was found (fig. 48), in comparison to laser used for HCl detection (fig. 35).

3. SO_2 detection in UV

Sulphur Dioxide is one of the gases, which emission need to be limited and monitored in coal-fired power plants under Large Combustion Plant Directive (LCPD). NDIR Continuous Emission Monitoring Systems (CEMS) have problem with detecting SO_2 , because strongest SO_2 absorption lines around $7\mu m$ wavelength have heavy cross-sensitivity with water vapours (fig. 49).

Fig. 49. SO2 Filter response to 100ppm SO2 and 30% H2O. With 30% H2O applied, the SO2 signal has lost approximately 50% of its original value. With 100ppm SO2 applied the SO2 signal has lost 8% of its original value. Reproduced from Procal's report written by Francis O'Doherty "D#0269 SO2 GFC Theory and application 10_02_11.doc"

Recently UV range <300nm get some attention and funds: <http://www.riken.jp/lab/THz-device/images/semiconductortoday.pdf>, but all efforts are focused on uncooled LEDs, and there is hard to obtain even quotation, for UV LED with Peltier cooler.

Two main manufacturers of LEDs <300nm:

- <http://www.s-et.com/products.html>
- <http://www.ledwv.com/en/uv-led-c-19/>

Procal was interested in conducting tests of SO₂ detection in UV part of the light spectrum, to verify whether sensitive detection with inexpensive UV LEDs might be viable alternative to SO₂ detection with NDIR technique.

Fig. 50. Selected molecules, with absorption at UV, which could give cross-signals with SO₂.
 Source: prof Weidong Chen presentation at TDLS2013.

During the scope of Prophet project five consecutive attempts of refining UV SO₂ detection setup was conducted.

a) Direct detection of light passed through tube with SO₂ (Aug 2012)

Fig. 51. Picture of the first SO₂ detection setup

■ Spectral response

Fig. 52. Spectral response of S1226-BQ photodiode used to collect UV beam from LED

Fig. 53. Angular distribution of light from UV LED photodiode used in first attempt.

Fig. 54. UV LED driver made in Procal, and used during first attempt

Fig. 55. Electrical schematic of preamplifier used with S1226-BQ photodiode

System was quite hard to align due to lack of proper mounts for UV LED and lens. Maximal signal was reached due to trade-off between collection efficiency of light by lens, and proper focusing of beam into spot at mirror, which directs light into tube.

UV photodiode waveform was generated with square wave function generator 60Hz, 50% duty cycle.

Signal acquisition was following: acquisition started with rising edge of square function, and 150ms waveform was recorded (150 samples, with sampling time of 1ms/1000kHz).

Maximum obtained signal was ~40mVpp. There was a large distortion of measured waveforms when the fluorescent light was on, therefore artificial light was switched off during measurements, and during final measurements set-up was protected by metal cover on setup.

Area under the curve was used as a measure of absorption. Before calculation of area, set of data was lowered to average 0 level by subtraction of average from dark region 100-140ms.

Calculated area under the curve was plotted and recorded to file for further data processing according to Beer-Lambert law.

Fig. 56. Area under curve vs time during SO₂ measurements.

Initially reference level from 0 % of SO₂ was recorded (fig. 56), followed by 100% of SO₂ (1500ppm cylinder), and then again to 0 % of SO₂ with 20% step.

Area corresponding to 0% at the beginning and at the end of the measurement differs, which suggests, that prolonged measurements are not stable. The exact reason of 0% drift was not identified, as the system was disassembled.

Fig. 57. Area under the pulse, and Absorbance in mAU vs Concentration in ppm.

Calculated absorbance shows almost linear dependence on SO₂ concentration (fig. 57). Main drawback of the setup was sensitivity to ambient light, and small collection efficiency of light from UV LED.

b) Phase sensitive detection with lock-in amplifier and new LED driver (Dec 2012)

Based on first SO₂ measurements we tried to improve system setup, by making it more immune for ambient light and less noisy. Both improvements could be achieved by introducing phase sensitive detection technique with lock-in amplifier.

Frequency of the detection was severely impeded by slow response of UV current driver (max ~100Hz). UV manufacturer advice to use the diode with square pulse fill factor ~few percent. In connection with slow driver for few percent fill factor we get so large signal drop, that we decided to increase it to 30%.

I tried to improve UV light collection by introducing bigger lens collecting all diode radiation, but it turned out, that with bigger lens, I couldn't create low divergence beam inside gas cell, which resulted in large signal losses, and finally returned to optical system with small lens before UV diode.

Preliminary measurements in ambient temperature (sample and head temp = ambient) was very promising. 300ppm SO₂ cylinder allowed us calibration at 5 levels 300, 240, 180, 120, 60, and 0ppm (fig.).

Fig. 58. Signal vs time for SO₂ gas calibration experiment.

To study signal behaviour at lower changes, one of experiments tested analyser response to 30, 24, 18, 12, 6 ppm SO₂ changes (fig. 59).

Fig. 59. Small SO₂ concentration calibration. Levels correspond to 30, 24, 18, 12, 6 ppm SO₂ concentration.

As can be seen 6ppm SO₂ changes was easy to detect with analyser, but base level drifted constantly, despite relatively small ambient temperature changes.

Subsequently it was measured a series of long time experiments without gas to study 0 level stability.

Fig. 60. Zero level signal drift vs time.

Fig. 61. Zero level signal drift vs time.

Zero level measurements show (fig 60 and 61), that although there is a temperature dependence on UV power, the main reason of long term drifts is UV diode overheating and its slow degradation. 30% square pulse fill factor is too long, it should be closer to a few percent, as manufacturer suggest.

Measurement showed, that SO₂ detection in UV is a viable option, but to realise it and or prove it without any doubts another refinement is needed.

Fig. 64. Correlation of signal with ambient temperature.

To obtain even more stable light source, UV LED need to be independent from ambient temperature.

d) LED mount stabilisation with TECC (Jul 2013)

In this approach Peltier thermoelectric (TEC) cooler from Melcor, with PID TEC driver (Evaluation Kit for MAX1978 chip), was used to stabilise temperature of the UV LED mount (fig.)

Fig. 65. Mound made for UV LED. To part will have TEC cooler attached. Note black bar from material that is heat insulating, to avoid heat transfer from baseplate.

Fig. 66. Electrical components of setup, with wiring diagram.

LabView software was developed and improved with each approach to perform data acquisition from all sensors/components, and to save selected information to CSV files, which were analyzed in scripts written in R language.

Fig. 67: Labview software front panel

Fig. 68: Data acquisition part of LabView(LV) software

Fig. 69: Creating output files in LV

Fig. 72: Baseline stability during overnight test.

Fig. 71 shows, that when ambient temperature is stable, then we could expect fairly stable baseline, unfortunately long term measurements (fig. 72) show UV intensity fluctuations inversely proportional to ambient temperature.

Long term stability test proved, that with external TEC we have some protection from ambient temperature changes, but it is still not enough to provide stable UV LED signal. Roughly 40mV baseline change corresponds to ~30ppm of SO₂ change, which is too much. Thermistor should be better protected from pick-up noise, or bigger capacitor should be placed in parallel to provide better low-pass filtering of voltage signal.

It seems that the best temperature stabilization was between 10th and 13th of hour, but UV LED signal was still rising due to ambient temperature decrease.

Fig. 73: Intensity changes recorded during SO₂ gas test.

Fig. 74. Detector signal changes due to SO₂, with mixing ratio of SO₂ in cylinder (255.2ppm) with dry air. Levels: 0%, 20/120, 20%, 18%, 17%, 10% ,5%, 2%, 0% (peak due to purge of lines at the end of the measurements). Green ranges shows data used to calculate calibration coefficients.

Figures 73 and 74 shows big stability improvement in comparison to fig. 4 where all levels have slope due to UV LED intensity changes.

	SO ₂ /air ratio	ppm	Signal, V	Signal, mAU
1	0.00000	0.000	1.3601	0.0000
2	0.16667	42.533	1.2598	33.2830
3	0.20000	51.040	1.2415	39.6082
4	0.18000	45.936	1.2525	35.7789
5	0.17000	43.384	1.2589	33.5863
6	0.10000	25.520	1.3010	19.2947
7	0.05000	12.760	1.3314	9.2537
8	0.02000	5.104	1.3489	3.5790

Tab. 2. SO₂ gas calibration values, and corresponding signal on detector.

Fig. 75: Zoom of initial part of fig. 74.

Fig. 76. SO₂ concentration versus photodiode signal. Zero level is taken from first part of fig. 13.

Calibration curve in fig. 76 shows very good linearity of signal in function of SO₂ concentration.

Fig. 77. SO2 mAU as a function of SO2 concentration

Limit of detection could be evaluated from standard deviation of zero level signal changes during measurements. Standard deviation of unfiltered zero level equals to 2.5mV, and after 20point moving average $\sim 1\text{mV}$ (fig. 78), the corresponding limits of detection equals to 1.33ppm and 0.7ppm, respectively.

White/random and high frequency fluctuations could be averaged to a large degree as it has been shown in fig. 78.

Fig. 78. Zero level ranges from beginning and end of calibration. Black curve shows effect of 20point moving average on zero.

Zero level still isn't very stable. Perhaps balanced detection technique with two detectors, one before tube, and one after tube would allow, to keep stable baseline in presence of UV LED intensity variations.

285nm UV LED signal vs H2O

Fig. 79. UV signal changes as function of time for 0-40% of H2O.

Signal change due to 30% of H2O is ~10mV. Fig. 76 shows, that 10mV corresponds to ~ 1% of SO2 change (25.2ppm).

Current Procal NDIR CEMS working at ~7.42 μ m need to deal with SO2 vs H2O cross-sense of ~400% (fig. 49), therefore 1% of cross sensitivity (25.2ppm SO2 change because of 30% of H2O) seems like a big improvement.

e) UV LED on TECC with hemispherical lens (planned)

Thermal delay between UV LED and cold finger of TEC is too big with cooler attached to heatsink of UV LED. This delay sets fundamental limits to possible temperature stability of UV LED in this approach.

The only way to better stabilize temperature of UV LED, is to use UV LED, where LED chip will be placed on TEC or usage of balanced detection scheme. Contacted main UV LED manufacturers, and obtained quotation for UV LED without hemispherical lense, but with TEC 499\$/pcs.

I tried to obtain quotation for UV LED with lense and TEC, but cost of ~1k\$ was prohibitive, and decision was to put this on hold, until price for UV LED with TEC will become more affordable.

On one of the Prophet workshops I spoke with M. Kneissl from Ferdinand-Braun Institute, and he mentioned, that they should have soon available UV LEDs on TEC, but the contact was not pursued due to end of the Prophet project.

3. Electronic modules for TDLAS

Commercial TDLAS gas analyser as a product on market couldn't be built from bench-top scientific instruments. It would be too expensive, with inadequate profit margin. TDLAS gas analysers consist of several, key optoelectronic modules, like laser driver, waveform generator, TEC driver, lock-in amplifier, preamplifier with data acquisition and signal processing board, that need to be developed to make production viable. In recognition of this fact, a significant amount of time was spent on designing and prototyping of such optoelectronic modules. Training in area of design, test, and manufacturing of the electronic devices was the most valuable contribution of Procal team (Jonathan Parker, Hugh Lane) to pockdoc training in the scope of Prophet project.

1. Laser Driver

Research prototype of the laser driver was built using description and PCB layout provided by D.S. Durfee et al. in following articles [16], [17].

Fig. 80. Picture of the soldered laser driver prototype.

Key sequence	Send number, hex	Send number, int	Measured					Calculated				
			V DACG	V DACset measured	Vmon	Vreg	Measured LD current	Vreg-VDACG must be STABLE	Vreg-Vdacset	V DAC set calculate d 2 ref voltages	V DAC set measured	Difference
01E	0x0004	4	1.691	1.691	4.015	5.708	80.3	4.017	4.017	1.69	1.691	0.00
06E	0x2101	8449	1.705	2.222	3.5	5.725	70	4.020	3.503	2.22	2.222	0.00
04E	0x8000	32768	1.739	3.751	2.014	5.769	40.2	4.030	2.018	3.75	3.751	0.00
03E	0x4000	16384	1.716	2.72	3.017	5.739	60.3	4.023	3.019	2.72	2.72	0.00

Tab. 3. Measured and calculated voltages and currents verifying that laser driver operates correctly.

Fig. 81. 20 steps staircase-shape generated in PIC24FJ256GB110 and send through SPI commands sent to Laser Driver. Measured on Vmon output with LabView.

Because laser driver current is set by sending numbers to DAC, I needed to learn programming of PIC microcontroller to use laser driver, and this task was more time consuming, than assembling and soldering laser driver PCB.

To obtain quicker change of laser driver setpoint two capacitors in DAC stage were changed from $2.2\mu\text{F}$ to 2.2nF . This increased noise of the laser driver. Standard deviation of 4V level in fig. 81 is $\sim 3\text{mV}$, with $V_{\text{mon}}=4\text{V}$ current is equal to 80.3mA . This means that current fluctuations have std. dev. of $\sim 0.06\text{mA}$, which was too much, and original capacitors were soldered in again.

2. Waveform Generator

Direct Digital Synthesis (DDS) waveform generator is one of the electronic modules, that are needed for building TDLS-WMS gas analyser. To replace 2 bench-top waveform/function generators TG2000 used for preliminary experiments on TDLS-WMS, waveform generator capable of delivering 3 synchronized waveforms would be needed.

Digital waveform generators that was selected to build is based on AD9833 chips, and programmed to output the following:

1. the square wave (sync) runs at the same frequency as the triangle wave(tri) at 125Hz indicating the number of cycles of triangle waves to the sampling board which will be used to synchronize the laser and filter wheel timings together.
2. The 64kHz sine wave which must begin at the same point in time as the 32kHz dither

Testing of waveform generator wasn't finished due to running out of time for Prophet project in Procal.

Fig. 82. Top level electrical schematic of waveform generator.

Fig. 83. Waveform generator schematic, that have 3 analog grounds that could be shorted to test noise performance of the PCB design.

Fig. 85. Assembled PCB board of function generator

3. Thermoelectric Cooler Controller (TECC)

All lasers for gas sensing need temperature stabilization, which is most often achieved with TECC. To be able to design TECC, first MAX1978 evaluation kit was bought, analysed and tested in prototype setup for temperature stabilization of UV LED for SO₂ detection.

Designed PCB layout for TECC based on MAX1978 (fig. 86), but this chip required expensive 4-layered PCB, therefore for TECC prototyping different chip was selected. LTC1923 chip is available in through hole package, and could be layout on standard 2-layered PCB. This chip was used to design PVM preamplifier/TEC board on fig. 99.

Fig. 86. Layout of TECC based on MAX1978 chip

4. Non-Dispersive Infrared (NDIR)

Location of ER in Procal was also a unique opportunity to obtain a wider overview of gas sensing techniques, especially NDIR gas detection technology, that is developed in Procal for more than 20 years.

ER was invited to analyse theoretical and practical limits of NDIR detection using pyroelectric detectors, and propose improvements.

Analysis of limits of NDIR showed that a way to circumvent some of the inherent drawbacks of pyroelectric detectors in NDIR detection, might be an MCT detector. Preparations were made to test such detector in Procal analyzer, including design of mount and PCB board with preamplifier and TEC for MCT detector.

Moreover, algorithm with splines was proposed, as a way of fitting cross-interference response between channels, that have no fitting errors in comparison to currently used algorithm with polynomials.

1. Model of the pyroelectric detector-preamp

As a first step in assesment of NDIR theoretical limits, mathematical model of the pyroelectric detector with preamplifier was developed, based on information from webpages of pyroelectric detector manufacturers: InfraTEC and DIAS.

Simulation of pyroelectric detectors from material parameters through, responsivity and noise to detectivity of two types of preamplifiers: voltage and current ones.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P
1																
2		Tab1														
3			50/50	56/44	65/35	70/30	75/25	80/20								
4		TrFe, mol %	5.0E+1	4.4E+1	3.5E+1	3.0E+1	2.5E+1	2.0E+1	0.0E+0							
5		TrFe, %	5.6E+1	5.0E+1	4.1E+1	3.5E+1	3.0E+1	2.4E+1	0.0E+0							
6		p, nC*cm ⁻² *K ⁻¹	4.0E+0	3.8E+0	3.6E+0	3.5E+0	3.3E+0	3.1E+0	3.0E+0	8.0E+0	1.6E+1	3.5E+1	2.3E+1	3.3E+1	6.5E+1	3.7E+1
7		ε' (f = 1 kHz)	1.8E+1	1.2E+1	9.0E+0	8.0E+0	7.4E+0	7.0E+0	1.1E+1	3.0E+1	4.2E+1	3.3E+1	1.8E+1	7.1E+1	3.8E+1	2.6E+1
8		tan δ *1,*3	3.5E-2	2.5E-2	2.0E-2	1.7E-2	1.5E-2	1.2E-2	5.0E-4	5.0E-4	5.0E-3	3.0E-3	1.8E-2	5.0E-4	1.8E-2	1.9E-2
9		c', J/cm3/K	2.3E+0	2.3E+0	2.3E+0	2.3E+0	2.3E+0	2.3E+0	2.3E+0	2.9E+0	3.2E+0	2.5E+0	2.5E+0	2.7E+0	2.3E+0	2.5E+0
21		Tab2		Det1	Det2											
22		Alpha		1.0E+0	1.0E+0		Temp., K	3.0E+2		Tab3	Current Opamp		Tab4	Volt opamp		
23		T_filt.(tau, f)		1.0E+0	1.0E+0		Cur. noise	5.00E-16		Rfb, Ω	2.40E+10		ReV, Ω	2.40E+10		
24		Power (phis), W		1.00E-6	1.00E-6		Volt noise	6.00E-9		Cfb, F	6.80E-13		CbV, F	2.00E-12		
25		Area, cm2		4.00E-2	4.00E-2		Cornet freq.	1.00E+1		tau_el, s	1.63E-2		param. tab.\$tau	2.00E+1		1.1E-1
26		thickness, cm		2.50E-3	2.50E-3								tau_el, s	4.8E-2		1.1E+0
27		gth, W/(cm*K)		4.31E-5	4.31E-5											9.9E+0
28		Gth, W/K		6.90E-4	6.90E-4											
29		Hb, Ws/K		3.10E-4	3.10E-4											
30		τ th, s		4.49E-1	3.62E-1											
31		τ el. Volt.Mod, s		4.80E-2	4.80E-2											
32		τ el. Cur.Mod, s		1.63E-2	1.63E-2											
33		Cp, F		6.1E-11	4.7E-11											
36		Tab5														
37		Det1 ULiTaO3		1.8E+1	4.3E+1	0.001	c', J/cm3/K	3.1E+0								
38		Det2 TGS		3.5E+1	3.3E+1	3.0E-9		2.5E+0								

Document allows to calculate Detectivity, Signal, Noise, Temp change of pyroelectric photo detectors from material parameters. Most of this parameters are given in Tab.1, they need to be copied to Tab.5.

Currently thermal conductivity of pyroelectric material, in tab2 has alues of gth from LiTaO3. This parameter need to be adjusted in case of different pyroelectric materials used.

D* for Current and Voltage preamps of detector from one pyroelectric material should be comparable, but signal and noise vs frequency are different

Current preamplifiers allows to introduce temperature compensation without sacrifice of S/N ratio.

Fig. 87: Material parameters of pyroelectric detectors.

Fig. 88: Detectivity of pyroelectric detector with current and voltage preamplifiers

Fig. 89: Frequency response of pyroelectric detector.

Fig. 90: Responsivity of pyroelectric detectors with current and voltage preamplifier.

Fig. 91: Noises of pyroelectric detectors with current and voltage preamplifiers.

Fig. 92: Step response of pyroelectric detectors with current and voltage preamplifiers.

Simulation shows, that pyroelectric detectors with current preamplifiers could be modulated with larger frequency, which is desired in NDIR application, where detector is used with narrowband filters on a wheel to up to 5 gas species simultaneously. Moreover, thermal compensation element does not lead to a reduction of signal and detectivity. Furthermore an incomplete illuminated pyroelectric element in current mode does not cause a loss of both signal and detectivity in contrast to the voltage mode.

Evaluation samples of temperature compensated detectors with current and voltage preamplifiers:

- LME-336-60, TO39 housing, thermal compensation, current mode, feedback 100G Ohm, CaF2 0.4mm thick window
- LME-316-60, TO39 housing, thermal compensation, JFET, voltage mode, CaF2 0.4mm thick

were acquired from InfraTEC, and suitable PCB board for easy integration into Procal analyzer test-bed was designed for LME-336-60 (fig. 93).

Fig. 93: Detector PCB board

2. TEC driver and preamplifier for MCT detector

An ultimate way to circumvent most of the inherent drawbacks of pyroelectric detectors such as slow frequency response, moderate detectivity, sensitivity to ambient temperature, microphonic noise, would be photon detectors. Currently, state of the art mercury cadmium telluride photodetectors for long wavelength infrared gas sensing are manufactured by VIGO System. Comparison of detectors shows that immersed and TEC cooled PVMI-2TE-8 detector could have detectivity (fig. 94) order of magnitude larger than pyroelectric detector, and superior ultra fast response speed, and temperature stability.

Fig. 94: Detectivity comparison of pyroelectric vs various PVM detectors.

To test TEC cooled PVM detector would require new mount, TEC driver, and preamplifier. Suitable mount attached to PCB with TEC driver and preamplifier was designed (fig. 95).

Fig. 95: Mount designed for PVM detector, and its PCB.

PCB of TEC driver based on MAX1978 designed for laser temperature stabilization in previous chapter required 4 layer PCB due to small footprint QFN48 of MAX1978 chip. Such design is very expensive for prototype produced in small quantities, therefore I decided to design another TEC driver based on chip LTC1923 (fig. 96, 97, 98, 99).

Fig. 96: The highest level schematic for TEC/preamplifier board for PVM detector.

Fig. 97: Electronic schematic of TEC section.

Fig. 100: Cross sensitivity example of SO₂ channel on H₂O (mAU series), polynomial and splines calibration curves.

Fig. 101: Error associated with polynomial fitting of calibration data points vs error using natural splines.

This technique, and errors related with it is excellently shown on prof. Tom O'Haver [webpage](#) [18], [19].

In practice the errors from the polynomial fitting may become comparable with hardware noise coming from detector + preamplifier + analog to digital converter.

To circumvent this serious limitation I investigated alternative approach to fitting called Natural Splines. Basically Splines are 3rd degree polynomials between each data point, which are then stitched smoothly on knots (data points). This fitting technique is used for example in vector graphics to render smooth, nice looking fonts from a few data points.

It allows to conduct cross-sensitivity correction with 0 error, as it is shown on fig 100, 101. It is numerically fast, and easy to implement.

Fig. 102: Spreadsheet with proof of concept, and natural splines algorithm applied into cross-sensitivity calculations

To facilitate spreading spline knowledge, and perhaps future adoption of this technique by Procal as cross sensitivity correction algorithm I developed a "proof of concept" spreadsheet fig. 102, with comparison of polynomial vs natural spline fitting algorithm.

5. List of skills gained or refined during Prophet project

- programming in R language for mathematical simulations, physics models, and analysis of measurements
- programming in LabView
- mechanical design – CAD software for engineering drawing
- optical design (SMETHODS trainings) and software used in Procal: OptikWerks
- substantial understanding of electronics design (practical PCB schematic and layout design (KiCAD)) and manufacturing
- electrical simulations with LTSpice
- laser-based gas sensing, measurement techniques, and their limitations
- unique insight into NDIR technique for gas detection

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